

Appendix Table 3. Dog element percentages for selected structures.

Structures selected for Tables 2-7 include those with the highest numbers of specific taxa, as well as a range of building types.

	Q-152 temple	Q-70 hall	Q-72 hall	Q-54 hall	Q-162 temple
limb	1.9%			0.8%	2.5%
metapodial/phalanges	5.8%	11.4%	7.1%	5.4%	23.0%
patella					0.8%
pelvis	6.9%	8.7%	5.8%	0.8%	0.8%
rib	5.0%	0.5%	2.6%	0.8%	1.6%
shoulder	3.1%	1.1%	1.9%	3.1%	0.8%
skull	35.4%	26.1%	35.9%	31.5%	33.6%
tarsal	1.3%	1.1%	1.3%	2.3%	0.8%
upper limb	11.9%	15.8%	17.9%	20.8%	9.0%
upper limb lower	16.2%	26.1%	15.4%	31.5%	15.6%
vertebra	12.5%	9.2%	12.2%	3.1%	11.5%